

A COMPARITIVE ANALYSIS OF ARMY WAVEFORMS & COMMERCIAL WIRELESS PROTOCOLS AT THE PHY/MAC LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

This paper will present a comparison of the basic resource definition in an OFDMA MAC/PHY layers for WiMAX and the TDMA/OFDM MAC/PHY. The majority of current radios in development for the US Army use TDMA/OFDM. This comparison will be conducted by defining and discussing the basic unit of system resource, e.g. the "slot". Following the protocol comparison, some simulation results comparing the performance of both systems will be provided.

1. INTRODUCTION

There is increasing interest in the Department of Defense (DoD), with regard to development and deployment of commercial wireless technologies for the battlefield of the future. The goals for using this technology are to leverage Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) hardware and software systems at a significant cost savings in R&D, as well as shorten timelines for deployment of this technology.

This paper will present a comparison of the basic resource definition in both an OFDMA system, e.g. WiMAX/LTE, and a TDMA/OFDM system. This comparison will be conducted by discussing how these two different communication systems define the basic resource (e.g. the "slot"), and how this resource is utilized in each system. In both types of systems, many slots are bundled together to constitute a "frame" or "epoch".

The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief definition of a slot; Section 3 provides a brief discussion on the advantages/disadvantages of a TDMA/OFDM system; Section 4 provides a brief discussion on the advantages/disadvantages of an OFDMA system; Section 5 provides simulation results comparing the performance of both systems; Section 6 discusses some other work that has been done to compare TDMA/OFDM to OFDMA; Section 7 reviews the simulation results; Section 8 concludes this paper and discusses options for future work.

2. SLOT DEFINITION

We treat the slot as the basic resource unit, which a communication system manipulates in order to transmit and receive data. The slot is defined by the data that is carried within a number of subcarriers x blocks (symbols) of time.

Both systems discussed in this paper are based on OFDM. In OFDM, a channel is processed by a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) upon reception of data and by an inverse-FFT (IFFT) upon transmission. The IFFT takes the data channel and splits (modulates) the data across multiple, smaller subcarriers. The number of subcarriers and OFDM-based system uses is determined by the size of the FFT. For example, 1024 point FFT (1024-FFT), process a channel and generates 1,024 subcarriers.

Subcarriers are organized into four categories. Pilot carriers (or tones) are reserved to only do channel measurements. Guard carriers are reserved and no data transmission is allowed on them. Guard carriers are used to provide space between data carriers to prevent inter-carrier interference (ICI). Data carriers are used to transmit data. The final type of carrier is the DC carrier.

OFDM systems break up time into symbols. Symbols denote the time required to transmit/receive the data. The amount of time in a symbol is broken up into the cyclic prefix and the useful symbol time. The cyclic prefix is a portion of the end of the symbol that is inserted at the beginning of the symbol. This is done to allow multipath time to settle during reception of the signal. Symbol duration is on order of microseconds, e.g. 50, 100 μ s.

3. SLOT DESCRIPTION – TDMA/OFDM

Figure 1(a) is an (example) illustration of a slot in a TDMA/OFDM communications system. Slots in TDMA/OFDM can be 6–100 symbols in width, and from 256 – 1024 subcarriers in height. The example slot depicted in Figure 1(a) is constructed of 1024 subcarriers

x 100 symbols. There is generally some control information contained in the slot header data structure, while the rest of the slot contains user data. Section 3.1 discusses the advantages to be had when pursuing the TDMA/OFDM approach, while Section 3.2 describes the disadvantages of the TDMA/OFDM approach.

3.1 ADVANTAGES - TDMA/OFDM

There are several advantages to the TDMA/OFDM communications technology and systems whose design are based on this technology. First of all, there have been significant resources poured into research and development around this technology. This is existing work that can be leveraged to build communications systems, thereby reducing costs and time to market/fielding.

Another advantage of TDMA/OFDM system is the use of slot assignment protocols, to ensure that nodes in a network can obtain enough slots to transmit their data. A large amount of R&D has also been poured into various slot assignment and resource allocation protocols for TDMA/OFDM networks. These slot assignment protocols can also take QoS requirements and channel conditions when making slot assignment decisions, so the capacity of the system is used as efficiently as possible. Frames are then repeated in time to give nodes in a network multiple opportunities to transmit over time.

channel conditions and measurements done by nodes in a network. TPC adaptation is beneficial because it allows for reducing power usage (good for LPI/LPD applications), reducing interference to other nodes in the network, as well as possibly extending link range (i.e. coverage) a radio has in a network. MCS adaptation is beneficial because it allows a radio to adapt the capacity (data rate) of the communications channel. Both TPC and MCS adaptation are usually done on a frame-by-frame basis in TDMA/OFDM systems when considering omni-directional systems. In directional networking, TDMA/OFDM-based system TPC and MCS adaptation could be done on a per user basis.

Current military networks that are based on TDMA/OFDM support several network topologies include point-to-point, point-to-multipoint, and mesh networks. These networks are ad-hoc and support mobility, e.g. MANETs.

3.2 DISADVANTAGES – TDMA/OFDM

While there are a few advantages to the TDMA/OFDM for the MAC/PHY of a communications system, there are also some disadvantages as well. For example, TDMA technology has been around for a very long time and since its inception there have been many advances in the development of MAC protocols and channel access schemes for wireless networks.

If a user doesn't get an allocation of slots in a frame, then they have to wait until the next frame to request more slots. This can violate QoS of applications such as voice/VoIP, unless the slots/frames are really short. A short frame is one that is less than 100ms or 1,000 symbols (at 100µs/symbol) long.

The concept of slot in TDMA/OFDM is not a very granular way of defining the resource in a communications system. This poses a couple of problems, such as inefficient utilization of the resource and getting accurate channel feedback for other radio operations.

To demonstrate the inefficiency of the resource utilization in TDMA/OFDM, slot utilization efficiency can be calculated. Let us assume, that a slot is modulated with QPSK, which provides 2 coded bits / subcarrier, at a coding rate of 1/2. For a slot that is 1024 subcarriers x 100 symbols, the total capacity of the slot is provides 1/2 x 2 x 1024 x 100 = 102,400 bits or 12,800 bytes. Efficient use of this slot is achieved, when either whole packets or packet fragments, are packaged (or 'packed') in such a way that all 12,800 bytes of data are utilized. For example, if the user in this example only had 1000 bytes to transmit, then over 92% of the slot is not

Figure 1 – TDMA/OFDM (a) and OFDMA (b) slot

Both transmit power control (TPC) and the modulation/coding scheme (MCS) can be adapted over time in a TDMA/OFDM system. Adaptation is based on

utilized. Given the bursty nature of traffic, as well as a dynamic operating environment, it is highly likely that slot capacity will be underutilized.

Several functions in modern wireless communication systems radios are dependent on accurate feedback on the channel. Examples of functions and capabilities are adapting MCS and TPC, tuning of MIMO transceivers, interference mitigation algorithms, cognitive radio capabilities (e.g. coexistence, spectrum sensing), and adaptive hybrid ARQ (HARQ). For these functions to work, they need to make decisions based on channel measurements done over a small enough block of frequency/time where the channel state is not varying. The slot in a TDMA/OFDM system is a rather large block of frequency and time, in which the noise power and interference can vary dramatically. This makes it difficult for functions to adapt to the quickly changing channel conditions.

Slot assignment protocols require time to work to resolve contention between nodes in a network for slots in a particular frame. Bootstrapping is the process by which contention is resolved, and usually takes place at the beginning of the frame. Depending on the particulars of the slot assignment protocol and how a node treats its neighbors, this bootstrapping process can incur a significant amount of overhead. This reduces the data carrying capacity of the frame. Using the example that was presented earlier, a TDMA/OFDM slot could be 12,800 bytes. If 20% of its frame is dedicated for bootstrapping, the bootstrapping overhead could be 256,000 bytes (assuming bootstrapping and data slots use the same MCS).

4. SLOT DESCRIPTION – OFDMA

Figure 1(b) is an example/illustration of what constitutes a slot in an OFDMA communications system. Slots in an OFDMA system are generally 1-6 symbols in width and around 4-24 subcarriers in height. The example slot depicted in Figure 1(b) is constructed of 24 subcarriers x 3 symbols. Control information may, or may not be transmitted in each slot. Section 4.1 describes the advantages to be had when pursuing use of OFDMA, while Section 4.2 describes some of the disadvantages of using OFDMA.

4.1 ADVANTAGES – OFDMA

There are several advantages to using an OFDMA-based MAC/PHY. Significant resources are currently being poured into developing products (e.g. WiMAX, LTE) that will use OFDMA. OFDMA is

cutting-edge technology and represents the future of wireless communications.

In OFDMA, 24 subcarriers x 3 symbols represent one configuration of a slot [1]. A frame in OFDMA may be 1024 subcarriers x 50 - 200 symbols. The equivalent of a TDMA/OFDM slot represents an entire frame in OFDMA. Assuming 100 μ s symbols, in this example, if a node doesn't get an allocation in the current frame, it would only have to wait (at most) 5 – 20ms to get another allocation. This makes it easier to meet QoS constraints for applications like VoIP.

The slot as defined in OFDMA, is a much more granular resource than the slot in TDMA/OFDM. This granularity itself leads to more advantages for OFDMA, i.e. an OFDMA system is more flexible and responsive with regard to its operation and how resources are allocated within the system.

Because the slot is short, only a few symbols wide, it can be assumed that the channel state is static. Multiple sets of measurements then can be made over the course of an OFDMA frame. This allows for accurate feedback that can be used to tune various functions like MIMO, interference mitigation, cognitive radio functions, adaptive hybrid ARQ, as well as adapting TPC and MCS. In fact, with an OFDMA slot/frame, a system can adapt MCS on a user allocation by user allocation basis within the same frame, regardless of whether or not a directional networking system is being used.

Another advantage of the granularity of an OFDMA slot is that more efficient utilization of a system resource can be achieved. Put simply, a node is only allocated the minimum number of slots to carry the data it needs to transmit. Using the example in the previous section, only 112 OFDMA slots (that are 24 subcarriers x 3 symbols) would be required to transmit 1000 bytes of data, thus leaving the rest of the slots in the OFDMA frame to be assigned to other users.

An OFDMA frame does require that some portion of the frame be dedicated for control messages and overhead, just as TDMA/OFDM systems require some portion of the frame for bootstrapping. Let us assume that 20% of an OFDMA frame that is 1024 subcarriers x 100 symbols, is dedicated for control messages and overhead. In this case the overhead is only 2,560 bytes. So, even if the proportion of an OFDMA frame dedicated to control messages and overhead is the same percentage as the proportion of a TDMA/OFDM frame that is dedicated for bootstrapping, the OFDMA frame has a fraction of the overhead.

4.2 DISADVANTAGES – OFDMA

While there are several advantages to using OFDMA MAC/PHY, it comes with some significant disadvantages as well. OFDMA based technology is new, it has only been in development for the past 5-6 years and being deployed (in the form of WiMAX/LTE) for only the past 1-3 years. Because of the relatively short amount of time that this technology has been around, not enough time has been spent field testing the hardware/software of communication systems using OFDMA. There are significant issues, from a systems engineering perspective that remain to be solved (e.g. deployment strategies, network architectures, military profiles of commercially-based OFDMA radios, and platform configurations as well as MAC protocol signaling and OFDMA PHY parameter selection).

Most of the communication systems that are being developed for the military (based on TDMA/OFDM) support mesh and mobile, ad-hoc network (MANET) technology. This is generally not the case for communication systems that are being built around OFDMA in the commercial enterprises and standards working groups. This may change in the future, but that remains to be seen. [2] defines a relay node for WiMAX deployments that extends the coverage/capacity of the base station. Relay stations are capable of mobility, but the network is still a tree topology. If one wants to build a true, mesh network on top of an OFDMA, one may have to build their own, proprietary algorithms, thus making interoperability between different vendor's systems difficult.

5. SIMULATION CONFIGURATION

Simulations were executed to demonstrate the behavior of the TDMA/OFDM and OFDMA systems. In this section we described the configuration of MAC/PHY of both systems in the simulations.

In the both systems the PHY was configured with the following: 1024-point FFT (720 usable data sub-carriers), a 10MHz channel, 8/7 sampling rate, a cyclic prefix of 1/8, and the modulation was applied over convolution coding. The simulation environment supports the following modulation modes: 64QAM (rate 1/2, 2/3, 3/4), 16QAM (rate 1/2, 3/4), and QPSK (rate 1/2, 3/4).

The MAC model attached to the OFDMA PHY is based on the IEEE 802.16 [1] standard. The MAC model was configured using 5ms frames, the default frame size as defined in [1]. All other advanced features of the 802.16 MAC model (e.g. ARQ/HARQ, Sleep/Idle mode, packing, fragmentation, QoS) were disabled.

The MAC model attached to the OFDM PHY was a generic TDMA model. For the TDMA/OFDM system, two configuration modes were simulated; 1s frame and 100ms frame. Each frame had 100 slots, so the 1s frame was composed of 10ms slots and the 100ms frame was composed of 1ms slots. For the TDMA MAC model, no slot assignment protocol overhead was simulated. A static slot assignment plan was used to allocate slots to nodes in a fair manner.

The following formulas can be used to calculate [3] the channel burst rate for each modulation method and coding rate combination:

- (1) $F_s = \text{Floor}(\text{Sampling Rate} * \text{Channel Bandwidth} / 8000) * 8000$
- (2) $T_b = \text{FFT-Size} / F_s$
- (3) $T_g = (1/CP) * T_b$
- (4) $T = T_b + T_g$
- (5) $R = N * b * c / T$

Where F_s is the sampling frequency, T_b is the useful symbol time, T_g guard time, T is the total symbol time, N is the number of usable subcarriers (after pilot and guard carriers), b is the number of information bits per symbol, and c is the code rate. For 64QAM, 16QAM, and QPSK there are 6, 4, and 2 information bits per symbol (respectively).

Using formulas 1-5 the following channel burst rates available in the model, are listed in Table 1:

Table 1 – Channel Burst Rate (Mbps)

Modulation	Coding Rate	Burst Rate
64QAM	3/4	32.13
64QAM	2/3	28.56
64QAM	1/2	21.42
16QAM	3/4	21.42
16QAM	1/2	14.28
QPSK	3/4	10.71
QPSK	1/2	7.14

The models used to execute the simulation scenarios are part of the commercial modeling and simulation software package, QualNet Developer [3], produced by Scalable Networks. Six simulation scenarios were executed, broken up into two sets. Scenarios 1-3, demonstrate the effectiveness of the OFDMA and TDMA/OFDM configurations in a point-to-point link between a single transmitter and receiver.

Scenarios 4-6 demonstrate the effectiveness of the OFDMA and TDMA/OFDM configurations in a cluster, mesh network made up of five nodes. The footprint of the mesh-cluster network in scenarios 4-6 was 750 meters x 750 meters. A single node (Node 1)

that has a height advantage and does not source/sink any traffic in the network. For the OFDMA subnet, the node that is central in the network acts as an 802.16 base station. For the TDMA/OFDM subnet the slot allocation was configured to given equal capacity and opportunity to transmit to every node in the network.

In the Figure 2(a) illustrates the network topology utilized in scenarios 1-3 and Figure 2(b) illustrates the network topology utilized in scenarios 4-6.

Figure 2 – Network Topology for Simulation Scenarios

For each scenario, there were three subnets. One subnet used the OFDMA configuration with 5ms frames, and the ratio between the downlink and uplink portion of the OFDMA frame was set to 50%. The second subnet used the TDMA configuration with 100, 10ms slots for a total frame length of 1s. The third subnet used the TDMA configuration with 100, 1ms slots for a total frame length of 100ms. In the TDMA/OFDM subnets, a static slot assignment divided the number of slots evenly between each node in the subnet.

No QoS or any form of priority queuing was used in the simulations. Power, antenna gain, and channel capacity were kept the same between the OFDMA and TDMA/OFDM subnets. The only modulation coding scheme used was 64QAM at a $\frac{3}{4}$ code rate. Sections 5.1 – 5.6 describe Scenarios 1 – 6.

5.1 SCENARIO 1: LARGE FILE TRANSFER, POINT-TO-POINT CONFIGURATION

In this scenario, a traffic flow consisting of a single large file (1MB, 1×10^6 bytes) FTP file transfer, between the transmitter and receiver on the point-to-point link. The metrics collected were the total file transfer time and the throughput. Table 2 shows the results for the OFDMA system and both TDMA systems.

Table 2 – Scenario 1 Results

Channel Configuration Rate	Throughput (bps)	Transfer Time (s)
OFDMA	5,069,226	1.57815
TDMA (10ms slot)	519,422	15.40172
TDMA (1ms slot)	406,502	19.68009

5.2 SCENARIO 2 –VoIP SESSION, POINT-TO-POINT CONFIGURATION

In this scenario, a traffic flow emulating a VoIP session, at a 32 Kbps data rate with silence suppression turned off was executed between a transmitter and receiver on the point-to-point link. The metrics collected were the average end-to-end delay and jitter. Call setup signaling was not simulated for this scenario. Table 3 shows the results for the OFDMA system and both TDMA systems.

Table 3 – Scenario 2 Results

Channel Configuration Rate	Average E2E Delay (ms)	Jitter (ms)
OFDMA	5.01501	0.080139
TDMA (10ms slot)	92.32059	35.98432
TDMA (1ms slot)	9.32488	0.000660

5.3 SCENARIO 3 –VARIABLE BIT RATE, POINT-TO-POINT CONFIGURATION

In this scenario, a traffic flow emulating a variable bit rate video session (averaging 256 Kbps) was executed between a transmitter and receiver on the point-to-point link. The metrics collected were the average end-to-end delay and jitter. Table 4 shows the results for the OFDMA system and both TDMA systems.

Table 4 – Scenario 3 Results

Channel Configuration Rate	Average E2E Delay (ms)	Jitter (ms)
OFDMA	5.01997	4.13149
TDMA (10ms slot)	101.41452	80.05617
TDMA (1ms slot)	10.24739	5.08063

5.4 SCENARIO 4 –LARGE FILE TRANSFER, MESH CONFIGURATION

This scenario is built upon Scenario 1. For this scenario nodes 2-5 initiate a single, 1MB file transfer to only one other node in the network. These traffic flows were executed over the OFDMA and both configurations of the TDMA/OFDM subnets. The metrics collected were the minimum/average/maximum of the total file transfer time and the throughput. Table 5 shows the results for the OFDMA system and both TDMA systems.

Table 5 – Scenario 4 Results

Channel Configuration Rate	Min/Avg/Max Throughput (bps)	Min/Avg/Max Transfer Time (s)
OFDMA	1,325,150/ 1,644,357/ 1,968,935	4.06311/ 4.96992/ 6.03705
TDMA (10ms slot)	192,769/ 305,817/ 421,014	19.00172/ 30.25104/ 41.50025
TDMA (1ms slot)	80,079/ 131,409/ 197,699	40.46551/ 68.20435/ 99.90089

5.5 SCENARIO 5 –VoIP SESSION, MESH CONFIGURATION

This scenario is built upon Scenario 2. For this scenario, nodes 2-5 initiate a single VoIP session, at a 32 Kbps data rate with silence suppression turned off, to only one other node in the network. These traffic flows were executed over the OFDMA and both configurations of the TDMA/OFDM subnets. The metrics collected were the minimum/average/maximum of the average end-to-end delay and jitter amongst the four traffic flows. Call setup signaling was not simulated for this scenario. Table 6 shows the results for the OFDMA system and both TDMA systems.

Table 6 – Scenario 5 Results

Channel Configuration Rate	Min/Avg/Max Average E2E Delay (ms)	Min/Avg/Max Jitter (ms)
OFDMA	39.27714/ 46.50236/ 57.33985	18.86596/ 24.67846/ 20.76677
TDMA (10ms slot)	122.62727/ 122.62972/ 122.63551	36.77936/ 36.78218/ 36.78597
TDMA (1ms slot)	12.70687/	7.99610/

	12.70750/ 12.70784	7.99632/ 7.99649
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5.6 SCENARIO 6 –VARIABLE BIT RATE, MESH CONFIGURATION

This scenario is built upon Scenario 3. For this scenario, nodes 2-5 each initiate a traffic flow emulating a variable bit rate video session (averaging 256 Kbps) to one other node in the network. These traffic flows were executed over the OFDMA and both configurations of the TDMA/OFDM subnets. The metrics collected were the minimum/average/maximum of average end-to-end delay and jitter amongst the four traffic flows. Table 7 shows the results for the OFDMA system and both TDMA systems.

Table 7 – Scenario 6 Results

Channel Configuration Rate	Min/Avg/Max Average E2E Delay (ms)	Min/Avg/Max Jitter (ms)
OFDMA	49.69307/ 58.13061/ 67.5316	35.12814/ 38.71830/ 43.59459
TDMA (10ms slot)	125.73359/ 126.17561/ 126.39732	79.95209/ 80.19310/ 80.67129
TDMA (1ms slot)	12.92559/ 12.98478/ 13.12393	20.98817/ 24.52264/ 31.53417

6. REVIEW OF SIMULATION RESULTS

As the simulation performance results in this paper show, a radio based on the OFDMA is capable of providing comparable if not better performance than one based on TDMA/OFDM. The OFDMA system was able to achieve higher throughput in both the point-to-point and mesh/cluster scenarios. For traffic that is delay or jitter sensitive, the OFDMA system performed better than the larger frame/slot (1s frame/10ms slot) TDMA/OFDM systems in the point-to-point scenarios.

However, in the mesh/cluster scenarios, the OFDMA system performed slightly worse than the TDMA/OFDM with regard to delay-sensitive traffic. This is because the model used to simulate the OFDMA behavior is an IEEE 802.16 model, whereby subscriber stations (SSs) affiliate with a base station (BS). Each SS then relays its traffic through the BS. So, an extra hop and queuing delay is incurred when going through the BS.

7. RELATED WORK

Not much work has been done to compare TDMA/OFDM to OFDMA systems, to date. [4], [5], and [6] represent the some of the only work that has been done to compare the performance of both types of technologies. [4], [5], and [6] differ in scope, but all the research made use of several multi-access and resource allocation schemes when comparing TDMA/OFDM to OFDMA.

[4] looks at the performance from analyzing application traffic behavior from a flow-level perspective. The flow-based traffic model was used to analyze both OFDM-based systems. This model was developed by extending the multi-class Processor Sharing model from single-carrier systems. The analysis shows that that OFDMA system is better at exploiting multi-user diversity, e.g. OFDMA has higher scheduling gain.

[5] focused on analyzing the delay characteristics within the IEEE 802.16 QoS architecture. This analysis differs from the work in [4], because it was executed on a packet-by-packet basis, in order to see how well these systems can support delay-sensitive, real-time traffic. [5] shows that OFDMA is better suited than TDMA/OFDM, to supporting real-time traffic. This is because the analysis shows that the OFDMA was more effective at opportunistically assigning resources.

The research in [6] was conducted by the same researchers that produced [5]. [6] focused on considering cross-layer issues in scheduling algorithms. Delay, packet throughput, BER, and (channel) bit rate were used to compare performance between TDMA/OFDM and OFDMA systems. Under the same traffic profile (i.e. with identical delay characteristics), dynamic OFDMA system was able to achieve a lower BER and higher throughput than the TDMA/OFDM system.

8. CONCLUSION

The slot/frame structure for the OFDMA system is more flexible than its' TDMA/OFDM counterpart. This flexibility makes it easier to build in support for advanced wireless communication concepts such as adaptive hybrid ARQ, cognitive radio coexistence, cognitive radio spectrum sensing, tune MIMO transceivers, tune interference mitigation algorithms, multicarrier (e.g. channel bonding), as well as adapt MCS and TPC. In fact, some of the commercial wireless systems based on OFDMA are being designed to support these functions natively.

TDMA/OFDM-based communication systems that are being developed for the DoD do not currently

support some of these advanced operational capabilities. Adding these capabilities to DoD wireless communication systems is going to add complexity, be very time consuming, and very expensive.

The simulation results show that the OFDMA technology is capable of providing higher throughput than equivalently configured TDMA/OFDM systems. From the simulation results, OFDMA would seem to have comparable, if not slightly worse delay performance to TDMA/OFDM, in practical deployments. Current development of OFDMA communication systems, such as WiMAX (based on IEEE 802.16) and 3GPP2's LTE, operate in a point-to-multipoint mode and not in a mesh mode. Hopefully, in the future standards development will produce technologies that support mesh network MAC protocols that work with OFDMA.

Future work would entail doing more simulations by taking operationally relevant force structure, inserting commercial wireless technology based on OFDMA, and then applying the new network designs to a militarily relevant scenario. An appropriate scenario would contain operational mobility and traffic, and allow a more detailed understanding of how well the commercial technology can support current and future Army missions. The data from a simulation could also be used to help make design decisions when it comes to developing a radio based on OFDMA or leveraging a commercial implementation (e.g. WiMAX, LTE) for used by the DoD.

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